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MODERN ENDOCRINE-ONCOLOGY AND RADIOTHERANOSTICS

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Annotation. Radiotheranostics is radionuclide therapy based on the results of molecular imaging with various radiopharmaceuticals, allowing in vivo visualization (using single photon emission tomography (SPECT) and/or positron emission tomography (PET)), and then systemically and selectively influencing the pathological metabolic processes caused by pathological process. In recent years, thanks to advances in the development of nuclear medicine (an increase in the number of cyclotrons, SPECT/CT and PET/CT in medical institutions) and, above all, radiopharmaceuticals, radiotheranostics is developing very rapidly in the world. The emergence of new radioligands based on ^{177}Lu , ^{131}I , ^{225}Ac and other radioactive isotopes in the world has initiated a large number of clinical studies of radioligand therapy for neuroendocrine and chromaffin tumors, prostate cancer, etc. Radiotheranostics as a new and very promising area of nuclear medicine is perfectly integrated into modern diagnostic algorithms in the field of endocrinology and oncology. Intraoperative radionavigation methods can improve the efficiency and safety of surgical methods, external beam radiation therapy, and brachytherapy. In my opinion, the future of personalized medicine will largely be determined by the integration of radiotheranostics, multimodal imaging, intraoperative navigation and existing/new diagnostic and treatment methods in combination with applied genomic and post-genomic technologies.

Keywords: radiotheranostics; PAT; SPECT; endocrinology; oncology.

СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ЭНДОКРИНООНКОЛОГИЯ И РАДИОТЕРАНОСТИКА

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Аннотация. Радиотерапевтика — радионуклидная терапия, основанная на результатах молекулярной визуализации с использованием различных радиофармпрепаратов, позволяющая *in vivo* визуализировать (с помощью однофотонной эмиссионной томографии (ОФЭКТ) и/или позитронно-эмиссионной томографии (ПЭТ)), а затем системно и избирательно воздействовать на вызванные патологические метаболические процессы. патологическим процессом. В последние годы благодаря успехам в развитии ядерной медицины (увеличение количества циклотронов, ОФЭКТ/КТ и ПЭТ/КТ в медицинских учреждениях) и, прежде всего, радиофармпрепаратов, в мире очень быстро развивается радиотерапевтика. Появление в мире новых радиолигандов на основе ^{177}Lu , ^{131}I , ^{225}Ac и других радиоактивных изотопов инициировало большое количество клинических исследований радиолигандной терапии нейроэндокринных и хромаффинных опухолей, рака предстательной железы и др. Радиотерапевтика как новое и весьма перспективное направление ядерная медицина прекрасно интегрирована в современные диагностические алгоритмы в области эндокринологии и онкологии. Интраоперационные радионавигационные методы позволяют повысить эффективность и безопасность хирургических методов, дистанционной лучевой терапии и брахитерапии. На мой взгляд, будущее персонализированной медицины во многом будет определяться интеграцией радиотерапевтики, мультимодальной визуализации, интраоперационной навигации и существующих/новых методов диагностики и лечения в сочетании с прикладными геномными и постгеномными технологиями.

Ключевые слова: радиотерапевтика; ПАТ; ОФЭКТ; эндокринология; онкология.

Introduction. Radioisotope (molecular) imaging of thyroid pathology in the 1940s. laid the foundation and determined the vector of development of nuclear medicine throughout the world. It was endocrinologists who were the first to use radioactive iodine to treat thyrotoxicosis and thyroid cancer, laying the foundation for radiotheranostics as such. The term “theranostics” refers to diagnostic-based therapy. From this point of view, probably, any therapy can be considered theranostics, because no therapy, in fact, can do without diagnostics. The fundamental nuance of radiotheranostics is that radioisotope imaging allows, using single photon emission tomography (SPECT) and/or positron emission tomography (PET) methods of the whole body, to detect in vivo the focus(s) of the disease, using hybrid methods PET/CT, PET/MRI , SPECT/CT to establish their anatomical localization and metabolic features, and using object (voxel) dosimetry methods to assess the dynamics of accumulation/removal of a diagnostic radiopharmaceutical (RP), which will ultimately make it possible to carry out systemic radionuclide therapy with the expectation that tumor foci will selectively accumulate and will retain the therapeutic radiopharmaceutical, just as they did with the diagnostic one. Over the past seven decades, the list of diagnostic and therapeutic radioisotopes and the “smart” ligands labeled with them (metabolites, antigens, antibodies) for anatomical and metabolic imaging and subsequent precision radionuclide therapy of not only endocrine and oncoendocrine diseases, but also other diseases (oncology, cardiology, neurology).

Molecular visualization of various metabolism disorders. PET allows in vivo study of various metabolic disorders using targeted chemical compounds labeled with positron-emitting radioisotopes. The development of a research method consists of selecting a molecule of interest (substrate or analogue) and an effective method for labeling it with atoms ^{11}C , ^{18}F or others. A molecular substrate labeled with a radioisotope undergoes an enzyme-mediated metabolic transformation in the body with subsequent accumulation in tissues, which can be assessed over time and quantitatively (standardized uptake rate, SUV) using PET. Since the uptake of a targeted molecular substrate by cells is mediated by specific enzymes (such as chemokinasases, thymidine kinases, etc.), the accumulation of radiolabels in tissues reflects the degree of enzymatic expression in it.

Pet imaging of glucose metabolism. The most important molecule for providing cells with energy for many biochemical reactions is adenosine triphosphate (ATP), which is produced in mitochondria due to glucose metabolism through oxidative phosphorylation to provide energy for cellular life

processes. Brain cells work exclusively on the energy of ATP breakdown, while the metabolism of the myocardium and adipose tissue is the main source of ATP production. Increased glucose metabolism is found in tumor cells, and it is based on aerobic glycolysis, or the phenomenon of the so-called “Warburg effect”, in which intensive glucose metabolism is maintained even under hypoxic conditions. Glucose is mainly transported into the cell by diffusion through specific transporters in the cell membrane, and in tumor cells, mainly through the GLUT-1 transporter. In the cytosol, glucose is converted by phosphorylation with the enzyme chemokinase into glucose-6-phosphate, which is subsequently metabolized into carbon dioxide and water. It has been shown that the hydroxyl group on the second carbon atom is not required for phosphorylation by chemokinase. Deoxyglucose enters the cell and is converted into deoxyglucose-6-phosphate, but does not undergo further catabolism, accumulating in the cell. For PET/CT, a 2-deoxy-2-fluoro-deoxyglucose (FDG) molecule is used as a radiopharmaceutical, in which the hydrogen atom in the second position is replaced by ^{18}F for molecular imaging of glucose metabolism. Moreover, the bond between carbon and fluorine atoms is even more stable than the bond between carbon and hydrogen, and the chemicals are not recognized by chemokinase. As a result, in addition to glucose, FDG-6-phosphate, introduced as a radiopharmaceutical, accumulates in the cells. In tumor cells, increased glycolysis and high FDG uptake are also associated with increased activity of the aforementioned glucose transporter GLUT-1 (insulin-dependent) and intracellular chemokinase expression.

Pet imaging of bone metabolism. Due to its high affinity for calcium, sodium ^{18}F -fluoride is ideal for assessing bone metabolism. Sodium ^{18}F fluoride has demonstrated high bone uptake with good clearance into the bloodstream, leading to improved contrast in PET bone imaging (increased bone-to-background ratio). PET with ^{18}F -sodium fluoride is widely used to assess bone metabolism in oncoendocrinology for thyroid cancer, parathyroid tumors, osteolytic syndrome due to fibroblast growth factor FR23 neoplasia, orphan endocrinopathies and other endocrine diseases complicated by osteopathies. This method successfully complements osteoscintigraphy (SPECT), illustrating the activity of osteoblasts, allowing molecular visualization of osteolytic processes in bone tissue.

Conclusion. The most distinctive feature of molecular imaging and radiotheranostics is the ability to see a pathological process in vivo and assess its metabolism, potential threat to the health and life of the patient, thoughtfully

select management tactics, promptly adjust during treatment, assessing its effectiveness. At the same time, the forecast of effectiveness and potential toxicity can be assessed already at the diagnostic stage (SPECT/CT, PET/CT), and the management of these parameters is impossible without the development and implementation of individual dosimetric and genetic (radiogenomic) and metabolomic (biomarkers) studies. Thus, establishing a hereditary predisposition to the development of a disease makes it possible to predict the risk of its development throughout life, and biomarkers and imaging methods allow us to detect the disease at an early stage and establish its localization/stage, and promptly perform adequate treatment.

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